

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Toure**FIRST NAME:** Sidy Mohamed**PROGRAM CODE:** DSDD**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr Gulma**Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied: UK

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 17%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2021 on Windows 11)

List your 5 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Writing a good essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7-12)
2. Punctuation (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15-23)
3. American vs. British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 25-32)
4. Plagiarism and its implications (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34-39)
5. Style guide (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40-43)

FIRST STEPS IN WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

When I registered for the PhD in Sustainable Development and Diplomacy at EUCLID, I thought it was enough to choose a theme, start writing the thesis directly, and periodically consult my instructor. However, I underestimated the importance of punctuation, writing style, and layout. As a French speaker, I found the differences between American and British English to be not obvious.

By reading this first material, I learned that an academic essay is, first and foremost, a scientific work that must be consistent, coherent, and respectful of the rules and standards required at this level. I understood the issues related to plagiarism due to the use of works and ideas of others without giving credit to the author through notes in the text, footnotes, or in the bibliography. Through this material, I discovered the existence of an automatic and simple way to insert notes and references using powerful software called Zotero.

This document will cover five major concepts that I extracted from material 1 of the ACA-401D course, as listed above. This response paper summarizes my understanding of the concepts developed in the material and will serve as a basis for dialogue with my instructor.

2) WRITING A GOOD ESSAY

From a global point of view, we can categorize essays into two large groups: academic essays and other essays such as autobiographies, novels, newspaper articles...

Academic essays have a formal character and are subject to scientific standards of writing and publication. Academic essays seek to provide an answer to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7). Academic writings come from institutions recognized for the quality of their work. These are universities, research centers, laboratories, high schools, and learned societies.

To be sure to write a good essay, it is first important to identify our topic and to take stock through the collection of information on what is known on the topic, what is unknown or remains to be clarified, the materials that we will need for research and to argue our answers.

It is then important to make a plan to organize your ideas better and structure your work well. This organization will save time and effort by focusing on the essentials. Starting to write early and planning your time well is an asset.

The essay structure must be coherent and should include an introduction, a body, and a conclusion. The ideas, assertions, or hypotheses discussed must be supported by evidence. References are a good way to support our assertions and protect our essays against plagiarism. By the way, a quality essay comes from long reading and intense research, which should normally be reflected in the writer's notes. A good essay is also the result of several iterations and several drafts. You have to write, rewrite, and adjust your ideas to integrate new aspects or abandon others. The essay must be clear and understandable; for this, it must contain simple sentences and paragraphs that are not too long.

At the end of writing, it is advisable to take a moment to refresh your memory before proceeding with a critical rereading. This will considerably improve the quality of the document by ensuring, among other things, that the rules of punctuation, referencing, and layout are properly respected.

3) PUNCTUATION

This chapter aims to show the learner the importance of punctuation marks and their use in academic writing. Punctuation marks act as a compass that guides the reader through the author's vast ocean of ideas, helping him understand the meanings of sentences and concepts. They indicate to the reader the beginning, end, and logical flow of a sentence, the pause point, and the rhythm of reading.

The most commonly used punctuation marks in English are apostrophes, parentheses, commas, semicolons, full points, exclamation marks, question marks, ellipses, and quotation marks. In this dialogue, we will look at three of the most significant:

a) Apostrophe

Unlike in French, where the apostrophe is used when two vowels follow each other at the junction of two words, the apostrophe in English announces a possession or a contraction. Possession is expressed in several ways:

- **By placings after a proper or plural noun that does not end in s.** examples: student's uniform, women's rights;
- **By placing ' after a plural noun that ends in s.** Example: teachers' office;
- **By placing or ' at the end of the final part in the case of compound nouns.** Example: Ernest Young and partners' meeting

As for contraction, it is important to specify that it is not allowed in academic writing. Example: my daughter wouldn't (would not) like milk.

b) Semicolon

We use a semicolon to link two related parts of a sentence, neither of which depends logically on the other, and each of which could stand alone as a grammatically complete sentence (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 18). Semi-colons can used in the following ways:

- **To link sentences that are closely related.** Example: The illness struck the young athlete after the competition; doctors worked hard to treat him.
- **To link sentences that are in opposition to each other.** Example: The river was rough; despite this, the canoes sailed.
- **To separate items in a list.** Example: The auditor's assessment is to verify that all transactions are recorded, ensure that management procedures are respected, verify the conformity and reliability of the financial statements, and certify the company's accounts.

c) Quotation marks

For me, quotation marks are the most important punctuation marks in academic writing because they allow us to give credit to others' works when we borrow their ideas in quotes and, therefore, help avoid plagiarism.

This course highlights two types of quotation marks: single quotation marks and double quotation marks. Single quotation marks are used to indicate direct speech or a quote, and double quotation marks are used in the same situations within single quotation marks. Example: 'My daughter is terrified of thunder', reports my wife, 'she read in a book "The farmer was struck by lightning in the middle of his field"'.

Single quotation marks can be used to indicate small titles such as titles of chapters in a book, titles of songs, or periodical articles. Example: one of the chapters in my father's bibliography is 'The Blacksmith's Journey'. We can make a quote clearer by rewriting it without quotation marks and using the form 'he said'.

4) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

Initially, I thought that British was the most widely spoken variant of English in the world, given the vastness of the British colonial empire. While reading this course, I discovered that since the end of the Second World War, American English has spread worldwide with the growing influence of American politics, economics, technology, and culture. For example, 70% of native English speakers speak American English compared to 17% for British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 25). American English is governed by Standard American English (SAE) and British is governed by Standard British English (SBE). Despite some differences, the two variants remain similar, mainly in education and science. The main points of divergence between the two variants are:

- **Different Pronunciation, Although Same Spelling.** Example: laboratory, schedule, dynasty.
- **Different Spelling, Although Same Pronunciation.** Example: Axe — ax; plough — plow; colour — color.
- **Same Term, Different but Similar Spelling and Pronunciation.** Example: Maths (SBE) – Math (SAE), Aluminium (SBE) — aluminum (SAE).
- **Same Words, But Different or Additional Meanings**
- **Differences in Usage with SBE 'Large Collective Nouns.** Example: (U.S.) Finnair has a flight to London today. (G.B.) Finnair has a flight to London today.
- **Differences in Usage with SBE 'Pluralised Adjectives.** Example: SAE: John failed his drug test and will be excluded from the team. SBE: John failed his drug test and will be excluded from the team.

However, both variants of English are accepted in EUCLID's academic writings, and they are enough to be consistent.

5) PLAGIARISM AND ITS IMPLICATIONS

Plagiarism is using someone else's information without giving credit to the author or source by referencing it in your paper. Having someone else or Artificial Intelligence do your assignment and then writing your name down before submitting it to your instructor is also a form of plagiarism.

Plagiarism is an academic offense that is severely punished. Its consequences can start from the reduction of the mark to the exclusion of the academic circle. There are two main ways to borrow information from other sources: quotation and paraphrase. Quotation involves repeating the exact words of a source to better persuade the reader, while paraphrasing involves writing the ideas of a source in your own words and style. It is important to be careful not to fall into the trap of plagiarism. Whenever we use a quote or paraphrase another person's ideas, we must reference them either directly in the text or in the footnotes.

In-text referencing consists of indicating in the parentheses just after a quote the name of the author or source and the number of the page concerned. For quotes longer than four lines, it is best to write them indented in small paragraphs without quotation marks. In this case, the quote is preceded by the author's name, the source's name, and the publication date. It is also possible to use a signal phrase to introduce a quote by using the author's name and keeping only the page number in the parentheses after the quotation marks. For example, in its latest report on drugs, the United Nations indicates "the crime rate has doubled in disadvantaged areas since the emergence of drug cartels" (81). When referencing in the text, one must list at the end of the document the works cited (bibliography). For each book, cite the name of the author, the date, the title of the book, the place of publication, and the publisher. For a website: Author. Title of the site, name of any editors listed, date the URL in brackets (<URL>).

Footnotes can also be used to reference cited information using the following format: author name, work name (place of publication, author, year), and page. Using this method, there is no need to add references at the end of the paper.

The quotation rate is monitored by most institutions, so be careful not to abuse it and only use it when necessary (it can help you to persuade the reader). It is useless to reference general information which is known to everyone and found everywhere. For example, the Republic of Guinea obtained its independence on 2nd October, 1958.

6) STYLE GUIDE

The writing style is not just about punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary; it also includes aspects like sentence length, layout, depth of treatment of a subject, spelling, readership considerations, use of abbreviations, accepted terminology, use of symbols, voice preferences (active vs. passive), structure, paragraph numbering and indentation, the use of headings, the use of lists, and trademark or branding considerations.

Certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting, should not be written following the writer's style but rather that of the publication, company, or website associated with the writing. These institutions publish guides to improve the consistency and coherence of writing. Writers who follow a set writing style save much time on proofreading and editing, unlike freelance writers who must develop a writing style for each type of reader or publication.

Finally, the lack of a regulatory authority for writing styles in English leaves room for multiple style editors, depending on interests; among the most important are the BBC News style guide and the Chicago Manual of Style.

7) CONCLUSION

This first part of the ACA-401D course and its supports (videos, Zotero, Grammarly premium) allow PhD students in Sustainable Development and Diplomacy to acquire the basic knowledge to begin writing an academic paper. The main lesson of this course is that knowledge is never definitively acquired; it is a continuous process that is updated and adapted to different fields (academic, professional, technical, etc.). Basic notions such as punctuation, referencing in the text, footnotes, and endnotes, which we thought we had mastered or underestimated, can still teach us new things both by their content and by the preponderant place they occupy in writing academic papers.

ACA-401D is a gateway to the academic world. It teaches us the discipline of respecting the rules and organizing research work.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 5th ed. Washington D.C.: Euclid University Press.

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